

On Some Split-Complex Diophantine Equations

Katy D. Ahmad

Islamic University Of Gaza, Gaza, Palestine

Katyon765@gmail.com

Abstract:

The objective of this paper is to study for the first time the solutions of a linear Diophantine split-complex equation with two variables, where we find an algorithm to transform a desired equation to a classical equivalent system of linear Diophantine equations. On the other hand, split-complex Pythagoras triples will be discussed and handled.

Keywords: split-complex integer, split-complex Diophantine equation, split-complex Pythagoras triple.

Introduction and basic definitions

The concept of split-complex numbers (hyperbolic numbers) [1] is considered as a generalization of real numbers in a similar approach of complex numbers or neutrosophic numbers [2-3].

These numbers have many applications, see [4].

The concept of Diophantine equations in the ring of split-complex integers is still unstudied, and it can be considered as a research gap. From this point of view, we study the linear Diophantine split-complex equations, and we present an easy algorithm to handle solutions.

We start by recalling some definitions.

Definition.

We define the set of hyperbolic integers as follows:

$$Z_D = \{a + b\varepsilon; a, b \in Z, \varepsilon^2 = 1\}$$

Remark.

Z_D is a subring of $R_D = \{a + b\varepsilon; a, b \in R, \varepsilon^2 = 1\}$ the ring of hyperbolic numbers.

Main Discussion

Definition.

We define the linear hyperbolic Diophantine equation with two variables as follows:

$$AX + BY = C \text{ where } X = x_1 + x_2\varepsilon, Y = y_1 + y_2\varepsilon \in Z_D, A = a_1 + a_2\varepsilon, B = b_1 + b_2\varepsilon, C = c_1 + c_2\varepsilon$$

Theorem.

The hyperbolic linear Diophantine equation is solvable if and only if the following two classical linear Diophantine equations are solvable:

$$\begin{cases} (a_1 - a_2)(x_1 - x_2) + (b_1 - b_2)(y_1 - y_2) = c_1 - c_2 \\ (a_1 + a_2)(x_1 + x_2) + (b_1 + b_2)(y_1 + y_2) = c_1 + c_2 \end{cases}$$

Proof.

The equation $AX + BY = C$ is equivalent to:

$$a_1x_1 + a_2x_2 + \varepsilon(a_1x_2 + a_2x_1) + b_1y_1 + b_2y_2 + \varepsilon(b_1y_2 + b_2y_1) = c_1 + c_2\varepsilon$$

Hence:

$$\begin{cases} a_1x_1 + a_2x_2 + b_1y_1 + b_2y_2 = c_1 \dots (I) \\ a_1x_2 + a_2x_1 + b_1y_2 + b_2y_1 = c_2 \dots (II) \end{cases}$$

By adding (I) to (II), we get:

$$(a_1 + a_2)(x_1 + x_2) + (b_1 + b_2)(y_1 + y_2) = c_1 + c_2$$

By subtracting (II) from (I), we get:

$$(a_1 - a_2)(x_1 - x_2) + (b_1 - b_2)(y_1 - y_2) = c_1 - c_2$$

So that the equation $AX + BY = C$ implies the classical system:

$$\begin{cases} (a_1 - a_2)(x_1 - x_2) + (b_1 - b_2)(y_1 - y_2) = c_1 - c_2 \\ (a_1 + a_2)(x_1 + x_2) + (b_1 + b_2)(y_1 + y_2) = c_1 + c_2 \end{cases}$$

The converse holds directly.

Remark.

The system:

$$\begin{cases} (a_1 - a_2)(x_1 - x_2) + (b_1 - b_2)(y_1 - y_2) = c_1 - c_2 \\ (a_1 + a_2)(x_1 + x_2) + (b_1 + b_2)(y_1 + y_2) = c_1 + c_2 \end{cases}$$

Is solvable if and only if:

$$\gcd(a_1 + a_2, b_1 + b_2) \mid c_1 + c_2 \text{ and } \gcd(a_1 - a_2, b_1 - b_2) \mid c_1 - c_2.$$

Example.

Let us find a solution of the hyperbolic linear Diophantine equation:

$$(2 + \varepsilon)X + (3 - \varepsilon)Y = 1 + \varepsilon$$

The equivalent system is:

$$\begin{cases} 3(x_1 + x_2) + 2(y_1 + y_2) = 2 \dots (1) \\ (x_1 - x_2) + 4(y_1 - y_2) = 0 \dots (2) \end{cases}$$

The equation (1) has a solution $x_1 + x_2 = 2, y_1 + y_2 = -2$.

The equation (2) has a solution $x_1 - x_2 = 0, y_1 - y_2 = 0$.

So, we can get $x_1 = 1, x_2 = 1, y_1 = -1, y_2 = -1$.

This means that $X = 1 + \varepsilon, Y = -1 - \varepsilon$ is a solution of the linear hyperbolic Diophantine equation.

Definition.

We define the hyperbolic Pell's equation as follows:

$$X^2 - DY^2 = N; X = x_1 + x_2\varepsilon, Y = y_1 + y_2\varepsilon, D = d_1 + d_2\varepsilon, N = n_1 + n_2\varepsilon \in Z_D.$$

Now, we will transform the hyperbolic Pell's equation to the classical Pell's equations.

$$X^2 = (x_1 + x_2\varepsilon)^2 = x_1^2 + x_2^2 + 2x_1x_2\varepsilon = \frac{1}{2}[(x_1 + x_2)^2 + (x_1 - x_2)^2] + \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon[(x_1 + x_2)^2 - (x_1 - x_2)^2]$$

$$DY^2 = (d_1 + d_2\varepsilon)(y_1^2 + y_2^2 + 2y_1y_2\varepsilon) \\ = d_1y_1^2 + d_1y_2^2 + 2d_2y_1y_2 + \varepsilon(2d_1y_1y_2 + d_2y_1^2 + d_2y_2^2)$$

On the other hand, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2}[(d_1 + d_2) + (d_1 - d_2) + \varepsilon((d_1 + d_2) - (d_1 - d_2))] \cdot \frac{1}{2}[(y_1 + y_2)^2 + (y_1 - y_2)^2 \\ & \quad + \varepsilon((y_1 + y_2)^2 - (y_1 - y_2)^2)] \\ = & \frac{1}{4}[(d_1 + d_2)(y_1 + y_2)^2 + (d_1 + d_2)(y_1 - y_2)^2 + (d_1 - d_2)(y_1 + y_2)^2 + (d_1 - d_2)(y_1 - y_2)^2 \\ & \quad + (d_1 + d_2)(y_1 + y_2)^2 - (d_1 + d_2)(y_1 - y_2)^2 - (d_1 - d_2)(y_1 + y_2)^2 \\ & \quad + (d_1 - d_2)(y_1 - y_2)^2] \\ & \quad + \frac{1}{4}\varepsilon[(d_1 + d_2)(y_1 + y_2)^2 - (d_1 + d_2)(y_1 - y_2)^2 + (d_1 - d_2)(y_1 + y_2)^2 \\ & \quad - (d_1 - d_2)(y_1 - y_2)^2 + (d_1 + d_2)(y_1 + y_2)^2 + (d_1 + d_2)(y_1 - y_2)^2 \\ & \quad - (d_1 - d_2)(y_1 + y_2)^2 - (d_1 - d_2)(y_1 - y_2)^2] \\ = & \frac{1}{4}[(d_1 + d_2)(y_1 + y_2)^2 + (d_1 + d_2)(y_1 - y_2)^2 + (d_1 - d_2)(y_1 + y_2)^2 + (d_1 - d_2)(y_1 - y_2)^2 \\ & \quad + (d_1 + d_2)(y_1 + y_2)^2 - (d_1 + d_2)(y_1 - y_2)^2 - (d_1 - d_2)(y_1 + y_2)^2 \\ & \quad + (d_1 - d_2)(y_1 - y_2)^2] \\ & \quad + \frac{1}{4}\varepsilon[(d_1 + d_2)(y_1 + y_2)^2 - (d_1 + d_2)(y_1 - y_2)^2 + (d_1 - d_2)(y_1 + y_2)^2 \\ & \quad - (d_1 - d_2)(y_1 - y_2)^2 + (d_1 + d_2)(y_1 + y_2)^2 + (d_1 + d_2)(y_1 - y_2)^2 \\ & \quad - (d_1 - d_2)(y_1 + y_2)^2 - (d_1 - d_2)(y_1 - y_2)^2] \\ = & \frac{1}{4}[2(d_1 + d_2)(y_1 + y_2)^2 + 2(d_1 - d_2)(y_1 - y_2)^2] \\ & \quad + \frac{1}{4}\varepsilon[2(d_1 + d_2)(y_1 + y_2)^2 - 2(d_1 - d_2)(y_1 - y_2)^2] \\ = & \frac{1}{2}[(d_1 + d_2)(y_1 + y_2)^2 + (d_1 - d_2)(y_1 - y_2)^2 \\ & \quad + \varepsilon[(d_1 + d_2)(y_1 + y_2)^2 - (d_1 - d_2)(y_1 - y_2)^2]] \end{aligned}$$

So that $X^2 - DY^2 = N$ is equivalent to:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{1}{2}[(x_1 + x_2)^2 + (x_1 - x_2)^2] - \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon[(d_1 + d_2)(y_1 + y_2)^2 + (d_1 - d_2)(y_1 - y_2)^2] = n_1 \dots (I) \\ \frac{1}{2}[(x_1 + x_2)^2 - (x_1 - x_2)^2] - \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon[(d_1 + d_2)(y_1 + y_2)^2 - (d_1 - d_2)(y_1 - y_2)^2] = n_2 \dots (II) \end{cases}$$

Adding (I) to (II) and subtracting (II) from (I) implies:

$$\begin{cases} (x_1 + x_2)^2 - (d_1 + d_2)(y_1 + y_2)^2 = n_1 + n_2 \dots (1) \\ (x_1 - x_2)^2 - (d_1 - d_2)(y_1 - y_2)^2 = n_1 - n_2 \dots (2) \end{cases}$$

This means that to solve the hyperbolic Pell's equation it is sufficient to solve (1) and (2).

Example.

Consider the hyperbolic Pell's equation:

$$X^2 - (1 + \varepsilon)Y^2 = 1 + 2\varepsilon \quad (*)$$

The classical equivalent system is:

$$\begin{cases} (x_1 + x_2)^2 - 3(y_1 + y_2)^2 = 3 \dots (1) \\ (x_1 - x_2)^2 + (y_1 - y_2)^2 = -1 \dots (2) \end{cases}$$

The equation (2) has no solutions, hence (*) is not solvable.

Example.

Consider the hyperbolic Pell's equation:

$$X^2 - (2 - \varepsilon)Y^2 = -24 + 24\varepsilon$$

The equivalent system is:

$$\begin{cases} (x_1 + x_2)^2 - (y_1 + y_2)^2 = 0 \dots (1) \\ (x_1 - x_2)^2 - 3(y_1 - y_2)^2 = -48 \dots (2) \end{cases}$$

The equation (1) has a solution $x_1 + x_2 = y_1 + y_2 = 2$.

The equation (2) has a solution $x_1 - x_2 = y_1 - y_2 = 4$.

So that $x_1 = 1, x_2 = 1, y_1 = 3, y_2 = 1$.

Thus $X = 1 + \varepsilon, Y = 3 - \varepsilon$ is a solution of the hyperbolic Pell's equation.

Hyperbolic Pythagoras Triples.

Definition.

A Hyperbolic Pythagoras triple (X, Y, Z) is a solution of the Diophantine equation $X^2 + Y^2 = Z^2$; $X, Y, Z \in Z_D$.

Theorem.

Let $X = x_1 + x_2\varepsilon, Y = y_1 + y_2\varepsilon, Z = z_1 + z_2\varepsilon \in Z_D$, then (X, Y, Z) is a Pythagoras triple if and only if:

$(x_1 + x_2, y_1 + y_2, z_1 + z_2), (x_1 - x_2, y_1 - y_2, z_1 - z_2)$ are two Pythagoras triples in Z .

Proof.

As we have shown before:

$X^2 = \frac{1}{2}[(x_1 + x_2)^2 + (x_1 - x_2)^2] + \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon[(x_1 + x_2)^2 - (x_1 - x_2)^2]$, so that $X^2 + Y^2 = Z^2$ is equivalent to:

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2}[(x_1 + x_2)^2 + (x_1 - x_2)^2] + \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon[(y_1 + y_2)^2 + (y_1 - y_2)^2] &= \frac{1}{2}[(z_1 + z_2)^2 + (z_1 - z_2)^2] \dots (1) \\ \frac{1}{2}[(x_1 + x_2)^2 - (x_1 - x_2)^2] + \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon[(y_1 + y_2)^2 - (y_1 - y_2)^2] &= \frac{1}{2}[(z_1 + z_2)^2 - (z_1 - z_2)^2] \dots (2) \end{aligned} \right.$$

By adding (1) to (2) and subtracting (2) from (1), we get:

$$\begin{cases} (x_1 + x_2)^2 + (y_1 + y_2)^2 = (z_1 + z_2)^2 \\ (x_1 - x_2)^2 + (y_1 - y_2)^2 = (z_1 - z_2)^2 \end{cases}$$

So that proof is complete.

Example.

We have $3^2 + 4^2 = 5^2$, $5^2 + 12^2 = 13^2$ are two Pythagoras triples.

Assume that $\begin{cases} x_1 + x_2 = 5, y_1 + y_2 = 12, z_1 + z_2 = 13 \\ x_1 - x_2 = 3, y_1 - y_2 = 4, z_1 - z_2 = 5 \end{cases}$

Thus $x_1 = 4, x_2 = 1, y_1 = 8, y_2 = 4, z_1 = 9, z_2 = 4$.

So that $X = 4 + \varepsilon, Y = 8 + 4\varepsilon, Z = 9 + 4\varepsilon$ is a hyperbolic Pythagoras triple.

$X^2 = 17 + 8\varepsilon, Y^2 = 80 + 64\varepsilon, X^2 + Y^2 = 97 + 72\varepsilon$, we can see $X^2 + Y^2 = Z^2$ clearly.

Conclusion

In this paper, we have presented an algorithm to solve linear Diophantine split-complex equations with two variables by transforming it to an equivalent classical system of Diophantine equations.

Also, we find a criteria for Pythagoras triples in the ring of split-complex integers.

References

1. Deckelman, S.; Robson, B. Split-Complex Numbers and Dirac Bra-kets. *Communications In Information and Systems* **2014**, 14, 135-159.
2. Akar, M.; Yuce, S.; Sahin, S. On The Dual Hyperbolic Numbers and The Complex Hyperbolic Numbers. *Jcscm* **2018**, 8, DOI: 10.20967/jcscm.2018.01.001.
3. Smarandache, F., "Neutrosophic Set a Generalization of the Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets", *Inter. J. Pure Appl. Math.*, pp. 287-297. 2005.
4. Fjelstand, P. Extending Special Relativity Via The Perplex Numbers. *American Journal Of Physics* **1986**, 54, Doi: 10.1119/1.14605.